

AIR QUALITY

Understanding the composition of the air we breathe, and how it affects our health

THE AIR WE BREATHE

The atmosphere is composed of a **mixture of gases**, with the most abundant ones being nitrogen (78%) and oxygen (21%).

Argon (0.9%) is also present, along with other gases in trace concentrations, including ozone, water vapour, nitrogen oxides, sulfur dioxide, and greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide (~0.04%).

Some of these are essential for life, while others can be harmful to our health.

AIR POLLUTANTS

Pollutants in the air are compounds that can be harmful to humans, animals and the environment.

- **gases**, like nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and ozone
- **particulate matter**, like mineral dust, black carbon (soot), smoke and liquid droplets (e.g. sulfates)

DID YOU KNOW?

Air pollution kills **7 million** people per year!

WHAT WE CAN'T SEE

Tiny particles, known as **particulate matter (PM)**, are found in the air. These come from human activities (e.g. cars) or natural sources (e.g. deserts).

Particulate matter is very small and cannot be seen with the naked eye, and comes in different sizes. It is known as **PM2.5** and **PM10** according to the particle diameter (under 2.5 or 10 micrometres, respectively).

HEALTH EFFECTS OF AIR POLLUTION

Air pollution is a major cause of health problems and deaths in the world. When we breathe, particles enter our body. Larger particles generally come from natural sources and are easily stopped by our nose and throat.

However, smaller particles (like particulate matter) can reach the lungs and other organs, causing different health problems depending on the length of exposure.

SHORT TERM

- eyes, nose, throat and skin irritation
- coughing, breathing difficulties
- headaches
- respiratory infections, pneumonia, bronchitis
- allergies

LONG TERM

- respiratory diseases, like asthma and cancer
- cardiovascular diseases
- strokes
- central nervous system problems

“Air pollution is now the world’s largest single environmental risk.”

World Health Organization

MAIN SOURCES OF POLLUTANTS

AIR QUALITY IN EUROPE

In 2021, about 97% of the urban population in the EU was exposed to PM2.5 levels above those set by the 2021 World Health Organisation guidelines (source: EEA).

The highest PM2.5 levels are found in central and eastern European countries (particularly Poland), and in northern Italy.

PM2.5 levels in 2021-2022. Source: EEA
■ good ■ fair ■ moderate
■ poor ■ very poor

AIR QUALITY INDEX (AQI)

Understanding how polluted the air is and adapting your habits to protect your health

The **Air Quality Index (AQI)** is an indicator of how polluted the air is at a specific area. This depends on the concentration of different pollutants in the air, for example fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and ozone (O₃).

In 2021,

over 97%
of people in urban areas

were exposed to PM_{2.5} levels above those recommended by the World Health Organization

The AQI is published by governments and other authorities, and it shows how the air quality is at a given moment in a specific location based on what is recorded by air pollution monitors and information from air quality models.

Understanding what the AQI means

- When the AQI is **low**, it means that there is a low concentration of pollutants in the air, and the air quality is **good**.
- When the AQI is **high**, there is a high concentration of pollutants in the air,
- so the air quality is **bad**.

WHO IS MOST AFFECTED

Sensitive groups or those with health conditions are most affected by poor air quality, and should avoid outdoor activities when the AQI is high.

PROTECT YOUR HEALTH

When the AQI is high:

- Stay indoors as much as possible
- Wear a mask
- Avoid exercising outside
- Avoid high-traffic roads and peak hours
- Stay informed about pollution in your area

MAIN AIR POLLUTANTS

Pollutants in the air can be inhaled, and lead to health problems, depending on the pollutant type and length of exposure. Here, we explore some of the most common air pollutants.

PARTICULATE MATTER (PM)

Tiny particles in the air that can be inhaled. They are known as **PM2.5** (fine) and **PM10** (coarse) depending on the particle diameter, which can be below 2.5 or 10 μm .

PM can reach the lungs and bloodstream, and affect our health, causing respiratory (lung), cardiovascular (heart), and cerebrovascular (stroke) problems.

These particles can include black carbon (soot) from fuel combustion, dust (from deserts or construction), sea salt, liquid droplets and smoke, among others.

These air pollutants come from fuel burned by cars, factories, power plants, and homes (e.g. for heating and cooking), as well as from agriculture, fires and natural sources (e.g. dust storms).

OZONE (O₃)

A gas typically found in the stratosphere (ozone layer), but considered an air pollutant at ground level (troposphere). Along with PM, it is a major component of smog.

Ozone at ground level is mainly formed when other pollutants (e.g. NO_x, CO, volatile organic compounds) react in the presence of sunlight. It can cause respiratory problems.

NITROGEN DIOXIDE (NO₂)

A reddish-brown gas released in the air when fuel is burned for transportation, heating, industry, energy etc. It can react to form ozone at ground level.

It is one of the nitrogen oxide (NO_x) gases. Exposure can cause irritation to airways, and respiratory conditions.

CARBON MONOXIDE (CO)

A gas released when burning fuels like wood, petrol, and coal. It mainly comes from motor vehicles. When inhaled, it can damage tissues and cells as it prevents them from taking up oxygen.

It can cause difficulty breathing, dizziness and flu-like symptoms, while high concentrations can be deadly.

SULFUR DIOXIDE (SO₂)

A gas released when burning fossil fuels (such as for industry and energy) and from volcanic activity. It can cause respiratory problems.

MAIN SOURCES OF AIR POLLUTION

Transport

One of the main sources of air pollution is vehicles with petrol and diesel engines, such as cars, buses and trucks, as well as airplanes, trains and ships. These release pollutants like particulate matter (PM), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and carbon monoxide (CO). In Europe, about 40% of NO_x and PM_{2.5} emissions are linked to road transport.

Industry

Power plants, large factories, waste management and other businesses release air pollutants, such as SO₂ from fossil fuel use, as well as volatile organic compounds from industrial processes.

Agriculture

Farming and agricultural activities (like the use and production of fertilisers, the use of farm machinery, and livestock raising), release nitrogen compounds, methane and other pollutants.

Homes

Residential activities, like using energy for cooling or heating, wood burning in fireplaces and fuel stoves, release a wide range of pollutants into the air.

Natural sources

Volcanic eruptions, sand and dust storms in deserts, wildfires and sea salt spray are some of the natural sources of air pollutants, including PM, CO and NO_x.

ACTIONS AGAINST AIR POLLUTION

Our activities and habits are the main sources of air pollution. Small changes in our habits can go a long way to protect our health and help improve air quality. Here, find a few simple actions you can take.

1 WALK, CYCLE OR TAKE THE BUS!

Cars and other motor vehicle are one of the major sources of air pollution. Walk, cycle or use public transport, especially when travelling short distances. Also, choose routes with less traffic to reduce exposure to pollutants.

2 TAKE LESS FLIGHTS!

Airplanes contribute to air pollution and climate change, so avoid flying where possible. If you have to travel over long distances, you can use the train, bus or other forms of public transportation.

3 USE LESS ENERGY!

Burning fossil fuels to produce and use electricity releases air pollutants into the air. Small actions can help reduce energy consumption, for example: use energy-efficient appliances, use less energy for heating or cooling, turn off the lights and unplug devices when not in use.

4 STAY INFORMED!

Regularly check the AQI in your area. If the AQI is low, then the air quality is good and you can enjoy outdoor activities. But, if the AQI is high, it means that the air quality is bad, and your health could be at risk, so it is best to avoid outdoor activities.

5 REDUCE THE IMPACT OF CARS

Choose cars that pollute less and avoid idling when not using the car. Ensure that your car is properly maintained. Refuel at night, since gasoline gases can react with sunlight and produce ozone.

6 CHOOSE RENEWABLE ENERGY

Where possible, choose renewable energy, such as solar and wind energy, to reduce air pollution coming from fossil fuels use.

